

1 Ignoring cage-to-cage variability increases false positive results

2
3 Reid D. Landes; Department of Biostatistics, University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences, Little Rock, AR,
4 USA; rdlandes@uams.edu
5 21 August 2024

6
7 **Abstract.** Many animal experiments house multiple animals per cage. ANOVA is commonly used for these
8 experiments. When cage mates are of the same group, outcome responses can become correlated,
9 violating ANOVA assumptions. As the correlation increases, p -values artificially decrease leading to false
10 positives (Type I errors). Recording cage identifiers and including these in statistical analyses eliminates
11 the artificially decreased p -values. Data from large mouse studies align with theoretical results.

12
13 A great many animal experiments house multiple animals per cage (or enclosure). And commonly used
14 statistical methods for many of those experiments are ANOVA or two-sample t -tests. These statistical
15 methods assume all the animals are independent. However, the outcome responses from cage mates
16 tend to become more correlated the longer they are housed together and the more sensitive the outcome
17 is to external influences. The correlation manifests as cage-to-cage variability; that is, all other factors
18 being the same, the means of the cages will vary. Many experiments cannot or do not mix experimental
19 groups within a cage, but animal methods seldom describe this important “same-group cage-mates”
20 attribute when describing the experiment design. Appropriate statistical analyses account for cage
21 variability by including cage identifiers in the analysis. Ignoring cage variability in statistical analyses can
22 cause p -values to be too low, thus increasing the probability of incorrectly rejecting the null hypothesis (a
23 Type I error)¹. Here, we use real mouse data to demonstrate the perils of ignoring cage variability in the
24 usual ANOVAs and how correctly accounting for cage variability gives theoretically expected results.

25
26 We used data from Wolfer et al (2004)^{2,3}: they conducted a multi-laboratory, replicated study
27 investigating 3 mouse strains in 2 cage environments (total $N=432$ females). We partitioned their study
28 into 18 mutually exclusive smaller experiments of 24 mice in each (**Figure 1**). The objective of the smaller
29 experiments was to compare behavior among mouse strains A, B, and C, within a given cage environment.
30 Mice were co-housed for 1 month, and 20 behavioral outcomes were evaluated at the end.

31

1 of 2 Cage Environments			
Rack	Col 1	Col 2	Col 3
Row 1	AA	AA	BB
	AA	AA	BB
Row 2	CC	BB	CC
	CC	BB	CC

Figure 1. For each of strains A, B, and C, 16 female mice were available. For each strain, 8 mice were randomly selected for the enhanced cages. The “enhanced cage” experiment had 4 mice/cage × 2 cages/strain × 3 strains = 24 mice. The remaining 24 mice were in the “standard cage” experiment. These 2 small experiments were replicated 3 times for each of 3 labs; thus 2 experiments/replicate × 3 replicates/lab × 3 labs = 18 experiments.

32 For each of the 18 experiments and 20 outcomes, we used two methods on the resulting 360 datasets: a
 33 one-way ANOVA that had strain as the factor with mouse as the only source of biological variability, and
 34 a linear mixed model (LMM) that had strain as the factor with cage and mouse (nested within cage) as
 35 sources of biological variability. (By definition, a LMM has 2 or more sources of variability.) The usual
 36 ANOVA assumes all of the 8 mice in a group are mutually independent. But, because there are 4 mice in
 37 a cage, the responses from cage mates may be correlated, inducing cage variability. The usual ANOVA
 38 does not account for potential cage variability; whereas the LMM uses cage identifiers as part of the model
 39 to explicitly account for cage^{4,5}. From the LMM, we obtain estimates of both cage and mouse variability.
 40 (Here, we express variability in terms of cage and mouse standard deviations: SD_{Cage} and SD_{Mouse} .)
 41

Figure 2. ANOVA p -values from 720 comparisons plotted by the corresponding LMM p -values **(A)**. Type I error for ANOVA and Type I error and power for LMM plotted by the ratio of the Cage SD to the Mouse SD. Since ANOVA does not hold to nominal significance level, power calculations are irrelevant **(B)**. Loess-smoothed moving averages (and 95% confidence intervals) of the proportion of comparisons for which the effect size, $|d|$, was no less than the median $|d|$ across all 720 comparisons (purple) and for which the p -values (gray points) were $p \leq 0.05$ (red), with actual moving averages overlaid in black; these for the LMM **(C)** and ANOVA analyses **(D)**. Panels C and D also display the (same) histogram of $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$ ratios, with 58.3% of the datasets having non-negligible SD_{Cage} .

42 Within each of the 360 datasets, we made 2 pairwise comparisons of strains (e.g., A vs B and B vs C) on
 43 which to report, conducting 720 hypothesis tests for each method. Before analyzing the data from an
 44 experiment, we *cannot know* whether SD_{Cage} is negligible. Indeed, SD_{Cage} was *not* negligible in 58.3% of the
 45 360 datasets, and the ANOVA p -values were lower than the LMM p -values (**Figure 2A**). For the remaining
 46 41.7% of the datasets, SD_{Cage} was estimated to be 0, and the LMM and ANOVA p -values were the same
 47 (see points on the diagonal in Figure 2A).

48
 49 We evaluated the Type I error rate of these 2 analytic methods in a simulation study of this experiment.
 50 For the LMM analysis, we also evaluated power for detecting a $1.5 SD_{\text{Mouse}}$ difference in means between
 51 a pair of strains with a 0.05 significance level test. (This difference would have 0.80 power if all the mice
 52 were *individually* housed and analyzed with the ANOVA.) **Figure 2B** shows that as the ratio $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$
 53 increases, the Type I error for the ANOVA increases¹; whereas the Type I error for the LMM maintains the
 54 0.05 level. As $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$ increases, the overall biological variability in the experiment increases: this
 55 is reflected in the decreasing power of the LMM analysis.

56
 57 The difference between 2 means or magnitude of the effect size, $|d|$, does not depend on the relative size
 58 of SD_{Cage} . In **Figures 2C** and **2D**, the median $|d|$ was stable over the range of $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$. Presumably,
 59 the proportion of comparisons for which true effect size is 0 (a true null hypothesis) also does not depend
 60 on biological variability. But as biological variability increases, the probability of obtaining a significant
 61 result (regardless of whether the null hypothesis is true) should decrease. When using the LMM, the
 62 proportion of significant results drops as $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$ increases (Figure 2C); whereas the significant
 63 proportion remains unchanged with the ANOVA (Figure 2D).

64
 65 When cage variability is ignored in analyses of experiments with same-group cage-mates, the probability
 66 of Type I errors increases as cage variability increases. This is true for single and multiple hypothesis tests,
 67 and it does not depend on the size of the experiment, type of outcome (see Supplementary Material), or
 68 the distributions of outcomes (e.g., binomial, Poisson, and even -omics outcomes)⁶. Even in tightly
 69 controlled environments, cage variability often exists (histogram in Figure 2C,D and Supplementary
 70 Material). It is vital that researchers record and use cage identifiers in their analyses to account for cage
 71 variability⁴; they should also report on how animals are co-housed in their experiments. Unfortunately,
 72 external motivators for researchers to account for cage variability are limited, especially when usual
 73 analyses tend to give more “significant” results. Hence, readers should be aware of the consequences in
 74 results that have *not* accounted for potential cage variability, and reviewers should, at least, ask how the
 75 potential for cage variability has been accounted for.

76 77 REFERENCES

- 78 1. Zucker DM. An analysis of variance pitfall: The fixed effects analysis in a nested design.
 79 *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 1990 Dec: 50(4):731-8.
- 80 2. Wolfner DP, Litvin O, Morf S, et al. Laboratory animal welfare: cage enrichment and mouse
 81 behaviour. *Nature* 2004; 432(7019):821-822.
- 82 3. Wuerbel H. Cage enrichment and mouse behaviour [Data set]. In *Nature* (432(7019):821-822).
 83 *Zenodo* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869449>
- 84 4. Landes RD. More power for less money: Statistical, power, and cost analyses accounting for cage
 85 variability in same-group cages-mates experiments. *Zenodo* 2024.
 86 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13352607>.

- 87 5. Lentner M, Bishop T. *Experimental design and analysis. 2nd ed.* Blacksburg, VA, USA: Valley Book
88 Company; 1993.
- 89 6. Murray DM. Design and analysis of group-randomized trials. *Monographs in Epidemiology and*
90 *Biostatistics*, Volume 27; 1998.
- 91
- 92

93 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

94

95 **Example 1: Larger, replicated experiments.** Sometimes researchers will repeat an experiment multiple
 96 times, usually to show internal consistency of experimental results (or “reproducibility”). Though beyond
 97 the scope of this work, an appropriate analysis is to combine the data from all of the replicates of the
 98 experiment by including replicate as a random factor in the statistical model^{S1}. We partitioned the
 99 Wolfer et al. study into 12 experiments^{S2}. Each experiment consisted of 3 replicates of this scenario:
 100 Eight (8) mice from each of 3 strains were randomly selected from among the available mice. The first 4
 101 randomly selected mice from a strain were placed in the same cage, and the remaining 4 in another
 102 cage. Thus an experiment had 72 mice – 4 mice/cage × 2 cages/strain × 3 strains/replicate × 3
 103 replicates; see **Figure S1**.

104

105

106 For each experiment and outcome, we used two statistical analytic methods on each of the 240
 107 datasets: a randomized block ANOVA with strain as a factor and replicate and mouse as sources of
 108 variability, and a LMM with strain as a factor and replicate, cage, and mouse (nested within cage) as

109 sources of variability. (Note: the ANOVA in these two models is also a linear mixed model because it has
 110 two sources of variability, but does not include cage as one of those sources; so we continue to call it an
 111 ANOVA.) Within each of the 240 datasets, we randomly chose 2 of the three possible pairwise
 112 comparisons of strains on which to report; thus, 480 hypothesis tests for each method. Figure S1 shows
 113 results using the same analyses that were performed on the 24-animal experiments. And the
 114 conclusions are the same: ANOVA p -values are artificially decreased (**Figure S2A**), Type I error increases
 115 with increasing cage variability (**Figure S2B**), the proportion of significant results from the LMM
 116 decreases as cage variability increases (**Figure S2C**); whereas the same proportions remains unchanged
 117 from the ANOVA model (**Figure S2D**).

Figure S2. ANOVA p -values from 480 comparisons plotted by the corresponding LMM p -values **(A)**. Type I error for ANOVA and Type I error and power for LMM plotted by the ratio of the Cage SD to the Mouse SD. Since ANOVA does not hold to nominal significance level, power calculations are irrelevant **(B)**. Loess-smoothed moving averages (and 95% confidence intervals) of the proportion of comparisons for which the effect size, $|d|$, was no less than the median $|d|$ across all 480 comparisons (purple) and for which the p -values (gray points) were $p \leq 0.05$ (red), with actual moving averages overlaid in black; these for the LMM **(C)** and ANOVA analyses **(D)**. Panels C and D also display the (same) histogram of $SD_{\text{Cage}} / SD_{\text{Mouse}}$ ratios, with 61.7% of the datasets having non-negligible SD_{Cage} .

118 **Example 2: Weight and hormone outcome measures.** In the main article, we used behavioral outcome
 119 measures to illustrate the presence of cage variability. Cage variability also happens with non-behavioral
 120 outcomes. Here, we compare body and organ weights and fecal corticosterone metabolite
 121 concentration between two strains of mice under various cage enrichment housing plans^{S3,S4}. We
 122 partitioned the original study into 8 smaller experiments. **Figure S3** illustrates the smaller experiment
 123 design for comparing the 2 strains within a single cage enrichment. The smaller experiment had 3
 124 female mice / cage × 4 cages / strain × 2 strains = 24 mice. This smaller experiment was performed in 4
 125 cage enrichments and replicated 2 times; thus there were 12 smaller experiments. From each mouse, 19
 126 outcome measures were collected: repeatedly measured body weights at weeks 0 – 8, body weight at
 127 study end, organ weights from the brain, heart, liver, spleen, both kidneys, and both adrenal glands, and
 128 corticosterone metabolite concentration. We used two statistical analytic methods on each of the 152
 129 datasets (19 outcomes / experiment × 8 experiments): an ANOVA with strain as a factor and mouse as
 130 the only source of variability, and a LMM with strain as a factor and cage, and mouse (nested within
 131 cage) as sources of variability. **Figure S4A – S4C** provide the same type of results as presented in Figure
 132 S2A, S2C, and S2D. We did not perform a simulation study to evaluate Type I error for this experiment
 133 design as we did in the main article and for the large, replicated experiments above. The conclusions are
 134 the same as the other two examples.
 135

Room 1			Room 2		
Rack	Col 1	Col 2	Rack	Col 1	Col 2
Row 1	A	A	Row 1	B	B
	A A	A A		B B	B B
Row 2	B	B	Row 2	A	A
	B B	B B		A A	A A

Figure S3. For each of strains **A** and **B**, 48 female mice were available. For each strain, 12 mice were randomly selected for a given cage enrichment; for example, “barren cage.” The “barren cage” experiment had 3 mice/cage × 4 cages/strain × 2 strains = 24 mice. The 24 mice were housed in 2 rooms as illustrated above; however, room identifiers were not included in the data. Further experiment design details are in Bailoo et al. (2018).

137
 138
 139
 140
 141
 142
 143
 144
 145
 146
 147
 148
 149

Statistical Analyses

Analyses of outcomes. For the example in the main article and Example 2 in the supplementary material, the ANOVA was a linear model with strain as the only factor and mouse as the only source of variability. All other models (the LMM in the main article and the remaining models in the supplementary examples) were linear mixed models. For the ANOVA in the supplementary Example 1, replicate was entered as a random blocking factor (a source of variability), along with mouse; cage was excluded as a source of variability. All of the LMMs had the same factor (strain) and sources of variability that were included in the accompanying ANOVAs, but also included cage and mouse (nested within cage) as sources of variability. The LMM model for the main example was

$$y_{ijk} = \mu_i + c_{ij} + e_{k(ij)}$$

151 where μ_i is the mean of strain i , c_{ij} is the random error associated with cage j in strain i , and $e_{k(ij)}$ is the
 152 random error associated with mouse k nested within cage j in strain i . c_{ij} and $e_{k(ij)}$ are assumed mutually
 153 independent of each other, and both are independently and identically distributed normal with mean 0
 154 and variances σ_c^2 and σ_e^2 , respectively. The independent variables in the model were strain and cage
 155 identifiers. For the ANOVA model, we did not include cage identifiers; consequently, dropping the c_{ij}
 156 from the model.

157

158 The LMM model for supplementary examples 1 and 2 was

$$y_{ijk} = r_h + \mu_i + c_{hij} + e_{k(ij)}$$

160 where μ_i is the mean of strain i , r_h is the random error associated with replicate h , c_{hij} is the random
 161 error associated with cage j in strain i from replicate h , and $e_{k(ij)}$ is the random error associated with
 162 mouse k nested within cage j in strain i from replicate h . r_h , c_{hij} , and $e_{k(ij)}$ are assumed mutually
 163 independent of each other, and are independently and identically distributed normal with mean 0 and
 164 variances σ_r^2 , σ_c^2 , and σ_e^2 , respectively. The independent variables in the model were strain, replicate,
 165 and cage identifiers. For the ANOVA model, we did not include cage identifiers; consequently, dropping
 166 the c_{hij} from the model.

167

168 For all models, we used REML estimation of the variance terms (i.e., sources of variability) and estimated
 169 the error degrees of freedom with Satterthwaite's method. The variance terms were restricted to be
 170 non-negative; that is, no negative variance estimates. In the instances where the cage variance was
 171 estimated to be 0, the ANOVA and LMM return the same results. We did not check for violations of the
 172 normal and constant variance assumptions because of the many analyses that were performed, and also
 173 to imitate naïve application of these models. We recommend that researchers check these assumptions
 174 with their own data. Using the estimated variances for cage and mouse (the residual variance) from the
 175 LMMs, we computed the Cage SD / Mouse SD ratio as the square root of the ratio of these two
 176 variances. When plotting ANOVA p -values by Cage SD / Mouse SD, we used the ratio from the
 177 corresponding LMM results, as this ratio was not available from the ANOVA. The models were fitted
 178 with the MIXED procedure in SAS/STAT® software, version 9.4 (SAS Institute, Cary, NC).

179

180 *Moving averages of proportions.* To obtain the moving averages of the proportion of significant p -values
 181 in panels C and D of Figures 2 and S2, the p -values were ordered by Cage SD / Mouse SD. We computed
 182 the proportion p -values that were less than or equal to 0.05 in the first 100 ordered p -values, then
 183 moved the window of 100 p -values up by 1, computed the proportion again, and repeated this until the
 184 end of the ordered p -values. For the moving average of the proportion of effect sizes with an absolute
 185 value that was less than or equal to the median of all of the effect sizes, we performed the same
 186 procedure as for the moving average of significant p -values. For both these proportions, we also
 187 computed the exact 95% confidence intervals for the proportions. In R version 4.2.2, we used the `loess()`
 188 function to smooth the moving average of proportions and their upper and lower confidence bounds.

189

190 *Simulation studies.* We evaluated the Type I error rate of the ANOVA and LMM analyses in simulation
 191 studies of the experiments described in Figures 1 and S1. For the example in the main article and
 192 Example 1 in the supplementary material, the design matrix of the ANOVA and LMM models
 193 corresponded with the experiment designs of the examples. In each simulated experiment, all 3 strains
 194 had a mean of 0, and σ_{Mouse} was set to 1. In increments of 0.02, we increased σ_{cage} from 0 to 2 for the
 195 experiment in Figure 1 and from 0 to 1 for experiment in Figure S1 (the observed ranges from the real
 196 data), with 10,000 datasets per increment. Individual mouse errors, and replicate errors in Example 1,
 197 were simulated from a standard normal distribution, $N(0, 1)$. The cage errors were simulated from $N(0,$

198 σ_{cage}^2). We analyzed each simulated dataset with the two models: ANOVA and LMM. Since there were 3
199 strains, there were 3 possible pair-wise comparisons, but we randomly chose 2 of those on which to
200 report, since including all 3 would induce a correlation of results.

201

202 **Data availability**

203

204 The Wolfer et al. and Bailoo et al. datasets are respectively available from Wuerbel (2024)⁵⁵ and
205 Wuerbel (2024b)⁵⁴. The SAS code and R code used in producing the results and figures in this work are in
206 the Supplementary Material.

207

208 **FUNDING**

209 This work was funded in part by the National Center for Advancing Translational Science of the NIH under
210 grant UL1 TR003107 (PI: Laura James), and from the National Institute of General Medical Sciences of the
211 NIH under grants P20 GM109005 (PI: Marjan Boerma) and P20 GM109096 (PI: Judith Weber).

212

213 **SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES**

214

215 1. Frommlet F and Heinze G. Experimental replications in animal trials. *Laboratory animals* 2021;
216 55(1):65-75.

217 2. Wolfer DP, Litvin O, Morf S, et al. Laboratory animal welfare: cage enrichment and mouse
218 behaviour. *Nature* 2004; 432(7019):821-822.

219 3. Bailoo JD, Murphy E, Boada-Saña M, et al. Effects of cage enrichment on behavior, welfare and
220 outcome variability in female mice. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience* 2018; 12:232.

221 4. Wuerbel H. Effects of cage enrichment on behavior, welfare and outcome variability in female
222 mice. In *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience* (12:232). *Zenodo* 2024.

223 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13343242>

224 5. Wuerbel H. Cage enrichment and mouse behaviour [Data set]. In *Nature* (432(7019):821-822).
225 *Zenodo* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869449>